

STUDIES ON THE COMPOSITION OF PEPTONES. PART V.

BY SUDHINDRA NATH SEN

Peptones and protein hydrolysates have been fractionated by dialysis and average peptidal aggregates in these fractions have been determined. The size of these aggregates increases when glucose is added to the peptide solution at an alkaline *pH*.

The development of protein hydrolysates and amino-acids mixture, suitable for clinical use, has been one of the most important advances in medicine in the past few years. Recently the efficacy of an enzymatic hydrolysate of veal in quickly restoring serum protein after blood depletion in immunised horses has been reported from this laboratory (Basu and Sen, *J. Hyg.*, 1947, 45, 56). Such a treatment of horses before and after bleeding during the process of immunisation may prove significant, specially in the light of the observations of Wissler *et al.* (*J. Immunol.*, 1943, 47, 133; 1946, 52, 267) that the antibody production has a close relationship with serum protein.

A review of current literatures on the use of protein hydrolysate shows that different workers have obtained clinical improvements with products in which proteins have been hydrolysed to various degrees. A desired specification of such hydrolysate has also been recently recorded from this laboratory (Basu, Sen and Bose, *Pharm. J.*, December 28, 1946). But upto now, no definite knowledge exists as to what extent proteins should be hydrolysed so as to give maximum efficiency. So long as the hydrolysate does not contain a true protein, no danger is likely to arise by its parenteral use provided that the peptides, which often cause reaction, are not too large. Completely breaking the protein into its constituent amino-acids also appears to be unnecessary as no proof has ever been given that all proteins in alimentary tract are hydrolysed to biuret-free product before absorption (Van Slyke, *Science*, 1943, 95, 259). It is therefore probable that presence of certain aggregates or polypeptides in the protein hydrolysates is advantageous as it will save time and energy in preparing the first building stone in the formation of blood and tissue proteins (cf. Madden and Wipple, *Physiol. Rev.*, 1940, 20, 194; Fischer, *Naturwiss.*, 1942, 30, 665).

The usual method of determining the number of peptide linkages, and consequently the size of the peptidal aggregates in a sample of peptone or a protein hydrolysate, by estimating the increase in carboxyl or amino groups after complete hydrolysis by mineral acids, gives results which are far from the true picture owing to the product being a mixture of higher and lower peptides. Moreover, as the addition of glucose is an essential requirement in the use of protein hydrolysate in parenteral therapy and as glucose is known to combine with amino-acids and peptides at alkaline or neutral reaction, its addition would therefore increase the size of the peptides in the hydrolysate. Ambler (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1929, 21, 47) has shown that compounds of progressive complexity are formed in glucose-protein reaction depending on the conditions of experiments and as high as 10 moles of glucose may

combine per mole of amino-acid. Compounds with hexose components, joined through N instead of O, have been obtained by Brigl and Keppler (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1929, 180, 38). Enders (*Biochem. Z.*, 1943, 313, 352) obtained products from methyl-glyoxal and glycine in such complex forms that they could not be dialysed. All these show the possibility of increase in the peptidal size of the aggregates when glucose is added to a peptone solution thereby altering the nature of the initial product.

Hence in any work involving comparative studies with peptides, hydrolysed to different stages, it is necessary to find out a method by which these products could be separated and classified into fractions consisting of peptides of comparatively known size. It is also thought desirable to determine to what extent glucose increases the size of the lower peptides so as to influence the original nature of the hydrolysate. A study in these two directions was accordingly undertaken

Any protein hydrolysate can be separated into different fractions by salt precipitation, but even then it is practically impossible to determine the peptidal aggregates in the lower fractions owing to the high salt concentration. The other alternative method for determining the lower peptides is initial dialysis of the hydrolysate and subsequent estimation of peptide linkage in the dialysate. If the maximum size of the peptidal aggregate that is dialysable through cellophane paper of standardised porosity could be determined, this would for all practical purposes set a limit to the dialysable and non-dialysable fractions. MaBain and Stuewer (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1936, 40, 1157) have shown that cellophane paper when treated with $ZnCl_2$ solution (64%) acquires pores of definite size which are not altered on washing away the $ZnCl_2$ solution. In all experiments recorded below, $ZnCl_2$ -treated cellophane paper (No. 300) has been used.

EXPERIMENTAL

The hydrolysate or peptone solution for analysis was diluted so as to contain about 0.8% nitrogen (equivalent to about 5.0% protein). 5 C. c. of this solution were placed in a cellophane bag and dialysed against 40 c. c. of distilled water at 3° to 5°. After 24 hours the dialysate was collected in a flask and the test solution was again similarly dialysed for 24 hours more. Addition of preservative was not found necessary. Dialysis was generally complete after this period as judged by the nitrogen estimation of the dialysate. All the dialysates were mixed together. Initial carboxyl groups in the sample were determined by titrating 2 c. c. of the solution separately in 96% and 50% alcohol using in each case KOH solution of the same alcoholic strength. Difference between the two values gives the carboxyl groups in the peptides (Willstätter *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1921, 54B, 2988). 10 C. c. of the solution were then mixed with 10 c. c. of 6N-HCl and hydrolysed under reflux for 6 hours at 125° (Sen, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 283). In a peptide ($R...CONHR_2...CONHR_3...COOH$) the increase in carboxyl groups on complete hydrolysis for each COOH group, initially present, gives the number of-CONH-linkages

in the sample. Increase in carboxyl groups for initial acidity, equivalent to each c. c. of 0.1 *N*-KOH, gives the number of peptide linkages per molecular aggregate. Of course in solution, which contains peptides of different sizes, the results give an average figure. Similar experiments with the whole product and with the non-dialysable portions were also carried out. Results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Protein hydrolysed products.	Whole.		Dialysable portion.		Non-dialysable portion.	
	†Initial COOH.	No. of CONH-linkages.*	†Initial COOH.	No. of CONH-linkages*	†Initial COOH	No. of CONH-linkages*
Bacto peptone : dialysable N, 69.2% ; non- dialysable N, 30.8%.	(a) 1.21	4.2	(a) 0.80	2.3	(a) 0.21	4.7
	(b) 1.84	4.3	(b) 1.12	2.2	(b) 0.27	4.5
	(c) 1.50	4.0	(c) 1.54	2.2	(c) 0.34	4.6
	(d) 1.82	4.0	(d) 2.00	2.3	(d) 0.40	4.7
	(e) 1.94	4.2	(e) 2.70	2.4	(e) 0.47	4.7
	Av. 4.2		Av. 2.3		Av. 4.6	
Wittes peptone : dialysable N, 59.4% ; non- dialysable N, 40.6%.	(a) 1.13	4.9	(a) 0.56	3.9	(a) 0.10	6.0
	(b) 1.82	4.9	(b) 0.72	3.8	(b) 0.42	6.0
	(c) 2.24	4.7	(c) 1.13	4.0	(c) 0.77	5.7
	(d) 2.80	5.0	(d) 2.20	3.9	(d) 1.15	6.1
	(e) 3.01	4.9	(e) 2.51	3.9	(e) 1.70	6.0
	Av. 4.9		Av. 3.9		Av. 6.0.	
Protein hydroly- sate ; dialy- sable N, 98.99%.	(a) 0.80	1.4				
	(b) 1.13	1.5				
	(c) 1.76	1.2				
	(d) 2.11	1.2				
	(e) 2.50	1.3				
	Av. 1.3					

In order to find out whether glucose under the conditions of preparing protein hydrolysate for parenteral use (Basu and Sen, *loc. cit.*, 1947) increases the size of the peptidal aggregates, dialysed portions of each peptone and protein hydrolysates were adjusted to pH 7.8 and 5% glucose solution was added to above and then autoclaved at 15 lbs. for 25 minutes. 2 C. c. of each solution were dialysed in cellophane bags and nitrogen in different portions was determined. Since

†Initial COOH was calculated in equivalent to c.c. of 0.1*N*-KOH in 2 c.c. of the solution after deducting the free amino-acids.

* per average aggregate.

formaldehyde also reacts with amino-acids and peptides and increases their size (cf. Fraenkel-Conrat and Olcott, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 34) it was thought desirable to compare the effect of this reagent and of glucose on peptone dialysates side by side. The reactions of HCHO with the dialysates were carried out according to Fraenkel-Conrat *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 950). To 8 c.c. of the dialysate 1 c.c. of 3.4*M*-phosphate buffer (pH 8.2) and 1 c.c. of HCHO (37-38%) were added and the solution was placed at 70° for 4 days. The extent of reactions both with glucose and formaldehyde could be judged from the decrease in the Van Slykes amino-nitrogen from the initial value. Results are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Dialysates.	Av. No. of peptides linkages.	Total %N.	Van Slyke's $NH_2-N\%$			Dialysable N (as % of total N) with glucose. HCHO.	
			Initial.	Final with glucose.	HCHO.		
Bacto peptone	2.3	(a) 0.280	0.109	0.094	Nil	58.5	50.5
		(b) 0.360	0.140	0.122	"	55.5	52.1
		(c) 0.507	0.207	0.188	..	56.0	51.7
Wittes peptone	3.0	(a) 0.164	0.056	0.041	Nil	51.8	76.0
		(b) 0.309	0.110	0.081	..	55.2	70.2
		(c) 0.456	0.158	0.117	..	54.8	73.1
Protein hydrolysate	1.5	(a) 0.30	0.17	0.14	Nil	67.1	80.7
		(b) 0.37	0.20	0.16	..	67.7	82.0
		(c) 0.45	0.25	0.20	..	66.2	80.3

DISCUSSION

From the results so far obtained with products containing peptides of different lengths, it appears that on the average peptidal aggregates of five amino-acids residue (≈ 4 peptide linkages) or less are dialysable through cellophane paper No. 300 ($ZnCl_2$ treated). For all practical purposes, this aggregate of five amino-acids residues may be taken under conditions of experiments as the maximum size of the peptides that are dialysable through cellophane paper. The size of any peptide, of course, depends on the molecular weights of the amino-acids which go to form the aggregate. The arrangements of the amino-acid residues in the main chain do not

vary in different peptides, but the residual weights of different amino-acids which reside in the side chain are variable. If the space occupied by these residues in the side chain is greater than the space occupied by the main chain, the determination of the number of CONH will be of little significance in evaluating the size of the peptides. But as the distance between two -CONH- linkages is near about $7.0\text{\AA}$ (Astbury and Marwick, *Nature*, 1932, 130, 309) and as in no case the residues in the side chain extend beyond $11.0\text{\AA}$ from the main chain (Astbury, *Cold Spring Harbor Symp. Quant. Biol.*, 1934, 2, 15; *Kolloid Z.*, 1934, 69, 340) the length of the main chain in a peptide containing four -CONH- linkages will always be greater than the side chain spacing and this will be the main factor in determining the size of such aggregates. In a lower peptide, however, the side chain spacing may prove significant.

Oxidised glutathione may be taken for all practical purposes to represent a peptide of four -CONH- linkages. To test further the validity of the above experiments glutathione was oxidised by CuCl_2 according to the method of Lyman and Barron (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1937, 121, 275) and it was found to be 100% dialysable through cellophane paper. For want of pure higher peptide, non-dialysability of these products could not be tested.

The nature of aggregate formation after reaction with glucose, as judged by decrease in dialysable N and Van Slyke's $\text{NH}_2\text{-N}$, are quite different in each case. In glucose-protein reactions reduction in amino-N, as observed by the methods of Van Slyke and Sorensen, has been observed by various workers suggesting NH_2 groups being involved in the reaction (Kostychev and Brilliant, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1923, 127, 224; Borsook and Wasteneys, *Biochem. J.*, 1925, 19, 1126; Fraenkel and Katchalsky, *ibid.*, 1937, 31, 1695; Ågren, *Acta Soc. Physiol. Scand.*, 1940, 1, 105). If the amino groups are the only determining factors, the discrepancies in the results depending on the decrease in amino-N and dialysable N, observed with different hydrolysates could not be explained. Hence the huge increase in molecular size after reaction with glucose, must be sought of in some other type of reaction. It is, however, clear that the effect of either glucose or H.CHO in increasing the molecular size of the aggregate does not primarily depend on the initial size. Some form of group specificity in these types of reactions is apparent. H.CHO is known to react with amide, thiol, guanidyl and possibly with other polar groups in addition to NH_2 groups (Fraenkel-Conrat *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). Hence it is possible that glucose can also react with groups other than NH_2 group. Ågren (*loc. cit.*) and Schubert (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1939, 130, 601) have shown that glucose reacts with -SH group of cysteine. Since the bond energy of co-valent hydrogen linkage of -SH and -NH are nearly equal, i.e. about 87 K/cal (Pauling "The Nature of Chemical Bonds", Cornell University Press, 1944) possibility of combination of glucose with -NH groups also exists. In either case, aggregate formation will be independent of the amino-nitrogen. Increase in molecular size due to aggregate formation with H.CHO is not so great as that with glucose and this is due to the higher molecular weight of glucose in comparison with H.CHO. As the initial size of the peptides does not always count in the

formation of aggregates with glucose, the final product after the addition of glucose in any protein hydrolysate, used for parenteral therapy, should also be standardised with respect to the non-dialysable N.

C O N C L U S I O N S

Determination of peptidal aggregate in any protein degraded product, by estimating the increase of COOH groups on complete hydrolysis, gives a result which is far from the true picture owing to the product being a mixture of higher and lower peptides. Initial fractionation of the protein hydrolysed products can be effected by dialysis through cellophane paper which has been previously treated with $ZnCl_2$ solution so as to have pores of definite size. Maximum peptidal size, dialysable through such cellophane paper, has been found to be, on average, aggregates of five amino-acids. Awaiting further researches on the choice of membranes which will allow the separation of peptides on a more definite basis, the results embodied in the paper tentatively suggest a method by which the separation of peptides can be effected on a more definite basis than previously employed.

Addition of glucose and formaldehyde to peptone solution at alkaline reaction and subsequent autoclaving increase the size of peptides. This increase in the size of the aggregates has no close relation with the initial size of the peptides. Certain specific groups, besides amino groups, have been suggested to take part in glucose-peptone reaction.

BENGAL IMMUNITY RESEARCH LABORATORY,
CALCUTTA.

Received February 28, 1947.
